

Suspicion of Ovarian Neoplasm in the Setting of New-Onset Ascites and Elevated CA-125: The Role of Transvaginal Ultrasound in A Secondary-Level Hospital. A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: New-onset ascites in women without known systemic disease represents a relevant clinical warning sign that requires exclusion of intra-abdominal malignancy, particularly of gynecologic origin. In secondary-level hospitals, diagnostic limitations may delay evaluation, making structured clinical reasoning essential for timely decision-making.

Case report: A 33-year-old woman presented with progressive abdominal distension and dyspnea. Significant ascites was documented, with no history of hepatic, cardiac, or infectious disease. Transvaginal ultrasound revealed an irregular left adnexal mass measuring 5.0 × 7.0 cm associated with free fluid. Markedly elevated CA-125 levels (600 U/mL) were documented. Based on the integration of clinical findings, ultrasound features, and tumor markers, the patient was classified as high risk for ovarian malignancy (O-RADS US 5; IOTA malignant criterion M2), and was urgently referred to a tertiary-level gynecologic oncology center for definitive management.

Conclusions: The integration of clinical assessment with transvaginal ultrasound and serum biomarkers allows early suspicion of ovarian neoplasm and appropriate referral, even in a secondary-level hospital with limited diagnostic resources.

KEYWORDS: Adnexal mass; Ascites; CA-125; Transvaginal ultrasound; O-RADS; IOTA.

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INTRODUCTION

Ovarian cancer remains one of the leading causes of mortality among gynecologic malignancies worldwide¹. The absence of effective screening programs and the nonspecific nature of early symptoms result in a high proportion of cases being diagnosed at advanced stages, which negatively impacts prognosis and overall survival^{1,2}.

New-onset ascites in women without known hepatic, cardiac, or infectious disease should be considered a clinically significant finding that warrants exclusion of intra-abdominal malignancy. When ascites is associated with an adnexal mass, it represents a high predictive clinical marker for ovarian neoplasia, reflecting peritoneal involvement and an active

tumor microenvironment mediated by angiogenic factors such as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)^{3,4}.

Transvaginal ultrasound remains the first-line imaging modality for malignancy risk stratification in adnexal masses. Widely used standardized systems, including the International Ovarian Tumor Analysis (IOTA) Simple Rules and the O-RADS US classification, consider the presence of ascites a major criterion of malignancy, guiding timely referral and appropriate management^{5,6}.

Although carbohydrate antigen 125 (CA-125) has limited specificity in premenopausal women, its elevation gains clinical relevance when integrated with suspicious ultrasound findings and alarm clinical features. In this context, referral criteria to gynecologic oncology include ascites and elevated

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CA-125 levels as indicators supporting the suspicion of malignancy⁷.

In secondary-level hospitals, significant diagnostic limitations persist, including restricted access to specialized radiologic interpretation and advanced gynecologic ultrasound. In such settings, structured clinical reasoning is essential to identify patients at high risk for ovarian neoplasia and to avoid delays in definitive care. This case report describes the diagnostic approach of a young woman with new-onset ascites managed in a secondary-level hospital.

CASE REPORT

A 33-year-old woman, G0P0, originally from Veracruz, Mexico, and dedicated to household activities, was evaluated. Her medical history was significant for systemic arterial hypertension diagnosed two years prior, with poor adherence to pharmacological treatment. She denied previous abdominal surgeries, drug allergies, and personal or family history of malignancy. Menarche occurred at 16 years of age, with regular menstrual cycles of 30 × 5 days. She reported being sexually active since the age of 30. The date of her last menstrual period was November 4, 2025.

Seven days prior to admission, she developed sudden and progressive abdominal distension, accompanied by a sensation of abdominal pressure, fullness, and constipation, with preserved passage of flatus. She also reported dyspnea that worsened in the supine position. She denied fever, nausea, vomiting, weight loss, or abnormal uterine bleeding. At admission, she presented with marked abdominal distension and respiratory discomfort. A therapeutic paracentesis was performed, yielding a large volume of serous fluid, with partial improvement of dyspnea. Cytochemical and cytological analysis of the ascitic fluid could not be performed due to operational limitations of the institutional laboratory.

Given the clinical suspicion of a non-benign intra-abdominal etiology, laboratory tests, tumor markers, and abdominopelvic computed tomography were requested. The tomography study was performed but lacked institutional radiologic interpretation. Laboratory evaluation revealed a hemoglobin level of 8.7 g/dL, hematocrit of 30%, and platelet count of $848 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$. Tumor marker assessment showed markedly elevated CA-125 levels (600 U/mL), while the remaining markers were within normal ranges.

On gynecologic evaluation, the abdomen was distended due to ascites, with a positive fluid wave sign. Bimanual pelvic examination revealed a retroverted uterus measuring approximately 8 cm, with posterior cul-de-sac distension secondary to free fluid; adnexal structures were not clinically assessable.

Institutional endovaginal ultrasound was limited by the presence of abundant ascites. Due to the inability to adequately characterize adnexal structures, an external transvaginal ultrasound was performed, which reported

abundant free fluid within the pelvic cavity and an irregular, hyperechoic left adnexal mass measuring approximately 5.02 × 7.08 cm.

Based on the integration of clinical, sonographic, and biochemical findings, the patient was classified as high risk for ovarian neoplasm (O-RADS US 5; IOTA malignant criterion M2). An urgent referral to a tertiary-level gynecologic oncology center was issued for further staging and definitive management.

DISCUSSION

Early diagnosis of ovarian cancer remains a significant clinical challenge, particularly in young women and in healthcare settings with limited diagnostic resources^{1,2}. The nonspecific nature of early symptoms and the lack of effective screening strategies result in a substantial proportion of cases being diagnosed at advanced stages, which negatively impacts prognosis and overall survival^{1,2}.

New-onset ascites represents one of the clinical findings with the highest predictive value for malignant ovarian pathology, especially when it occurs in women without underlying conditions that could explain its origin. This manifestation often reflects peritoneal involvement and an active tumor microenvironment mediated by angiogenic factors, particularly vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), which plays a key role in increased vascular permeability and ascites formation in ovarian cancer^{3,4}.

In secondary-level hospitals, important diagnostic limitations persist, including the absence of specialized radiologic interpretation and restricted access to advanced complementary studies. In this context, structured clinical reasoning becomes essential for the early identification of patients at high risk of malignancy. Nevertheless, when new-onset ascites is identified, a comprehensive evaluation is mandatory to exclude other frequent etiologies, such as hepatic, cardiac, or infectious diseases, before attributing its origin to a gynecologic malignancy.

Transvaginal ultrasound remains the first-line tool for the evaluation of adnexal masses and malignancy risk stratification. Standardized systems such as the International Ovarian Tumor Analysis (IOTA) Simple Rules and the O-RADS US classification consider the presence of ascites a major criterion for malignancy and allow objective risk categorization. These tools facilitate clinical decision-making and timely referral to gynecologic oncology, even in resource-limited settings^{5,6}.

Although carbohydrate antigen 125 (CA-125) has low specificity in premenopausal women and should not be interpreted in isolation, its elevation gains clinical relevance when integrated with suspicious sonographic findings and the presence of ascites. In the present case, the combination of these elements allowed classification of the patient as high risk for ovarian neoplasm and supported early referral, avoiding initial surgical interventions by general gynecology

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that would not be justified in the context of a high suspicion of malignancy.

In this regard, the role of the gynecologist in secondary-level hospitals does not involve definitive surgical management, but rather the early identification of alarm signs, appropriate diagnostic stratification using standardized tools, and timely referral to tertiary-level centers. While abdominopelvic computed tomography is useful for assessing disease extension once malignancy is suspected, it does not replace transvaginal ultrasound as the primary method for initial risk categorization. Moreover, histopathological confirmation is not required prior to referral, as a high-risk sonographic classification alone is sufficient to justify specialized oncologic evaluation^{10–13}.

CONCLUSIONS

New-onset ascites in women without known systemic disease should be considered a warning sign that warrants prompt and comprehensive diagnostic evaluation aimed at excluding gynecologic malignancy. In secondary-level hospitals, systematic integration of clinical findings with transvaginal ultrasound and serum biomarkers allows early identification of patients at high risk for ovarian neoplasm and supports appropriate referral.

The use of standardized sonographic risk stratification tools, such as the O-RADS US classification and the International Ovarian Tumor Analysis (IOTA) criteria, facilitates clinical decision-making and helps reduce diagnostic delays, even in resource-limited settings. This approach promotes timely referral to specialized care and avoids inappropriate initial interventions.

This case highlights the importance of structured clinical reasoning and the role of the gynecologist as the first point of contact in the early detection of ovarian cancer, which may positively impact patient prognosis and the overall quality of care.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards. The case information was anonymized to protect patient confidentiality and was reviewed and approved by the Research Committee (CI-2025-052-HGC) and the Ethics Committee (CEI-2025-052-HGC) of the Hospital General de Cancún.

INFORMED CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images.

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